

PROBLEMS IN THE USE OF DIALECTS IN FILM TRANSLATIONS

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Annotation. The birth of the cinema was initially regarded with great promise as a universal method of communication. This was partially true in the era of silent films as there was no need for translation before the introduction of inter-titles. The images filmed may have contained distinct cultural markers, thus rendering them somewhat foreign to spectators outside of the source culture; however, these markers could be absorbed in the way a painting is absorbed. Without linguistic intrusion, it was possible for spectators of foreign films to simply identify characters in regards to their appearance. This identification could also be made easier if the spectator knew what culture the film was coming from, in the way that paintings are understood by virtue of the culture that produced them. This article discusses the problems in the use of dialects in film translations.

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Still in the silent film era, the introduction of inter-titles, narration or dialogue presented on a blank screen between segments of action, brought translation to film in a very basic way. Most inter-titles were not complex or lengthy in order to accommodate audiences of varying levels of literacy. This made translation somewhat easier because there was not as much need to translate style as is seen in the translation of literature. Aside from an absence of elaborate style (which was provided by the acting, rather than the inter-titles), the problems

of translating inter-titles are the same problems seen in translating literature. The translator had to choose whether to pursue a word for word translation, or a translation based on the general sense or the inter-titles in their source language. The fact that inter-titles generally were descriptive of the actions carried out on screen may have aided translation because the action could clarify or support any difficulties found in the source text of the inter-titles.

Recently, news broke that Hollywood plans to remake a beloved cult Japanese horror film, *Audition*. Although the source material will, naturally, be adjusted for a new market, many fans of the original are likely thrilled to hear that there will soon be a new iteration of the truly terrifying tale.

The American production will tell the story of a man named Sam Davis, a widower whose wife passed away about seven years earlier and is living with his son. A filmmaker friend encourages him to hold fake dating auditions to meet new romantic prospects, and soon he meets and falls in love with a ballerina. From here, the story takes an incredibly dark and grisly turn.

Horror fans are sure to appreciate this particular American retelling of this ghastly story, but adopting foreign hits into English-language films is by no means new. *The Ring* and *The Grudge* are two other Japanese horror movies that enjoyed massive domestic success in the United States. More recently, Director Spike Lee released *Oldboy*, a South Korean mystery thriller. A quick search into American hit films with foreign roots would reveal a huge number of movies, in many genres, that began as foreign language productions. How, then, do filmmakers go about translating not just the actual language of a script, but transplanting a movie experience from one culture to a totally different one, while still remaining true to the story?

Translation must focus on much more than vocabulary and grammar – it needs to prioritize cultural variance. Films rely heavily on the emotional

investment of the audience into characters and plot lines. Filmmakers need the people watching the movie to care what happens, but, sometimes, cultural differences can impede that endeavor.

Consider some of the extremely different values between certain cultures. A conflict in a Japanese production which concerns the critical importance of the family unit and collective action probably will not interest many Americans, who typically champion rugged, lone rebel figures. Similarly, an American film that paints a vivacious, independent woman as a self-made hero will not find a welcome audience in certain socially conservative, Middle Eastern communities who value traditional, more subservient female roles. So, to navigate and offset some of these wildly disparate cultural norms, it is necessary to know the exact right words to use at every moment of the film.

ranslators also have to attempt to maintain the general tone of original work. There can be some major cultural differences that make this a very difficult task. Idioms, expressions, jokes, and sarcastic remarks can be some of the most challenging.

For instance, American humor is notorious for its heavy employment of sarcasm. Japanese culture has no equivalent for sarcasm. So, while an American might joke in English, “I *love* the DMV,” a literal Japanese translation would end up communicating that the speaker sincerely adores the DMV. Idioms can also be difficult and the translator must “go the extra mile” to ensure correct meanings. No, the translator walking an extra mile will have no effect on the meaning. See?

When there is a word-for-word match, translation is very easy, but sometimes specific words themselves simply do not translate. They have no true equivalent in another language.

One example is the Yiddish word, “Shlimazl.” In Yiddish, it refers to a person who is constantly and unfailingly unlucky. The Scottish verb “to tattle” literally means to hesitate when trying to remember a person’s name.

Communicating these ideas requires several English words, or full phrases.

However, it can also be a problem when there are several words in another language and only one English word is used to describe them. In Hindi, love can be “Mohabbat” or “Ishq,” or “Pyar.” But in English we only have one word, “love.” This can be inadequate when trying to express the nuances that exist for “love” in Hindi. In translating a romantic film, this might clearly prove to be very important.

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